

Legend

- Flushing Tunnel
- Missing Data (See Note 2)
- Infilled Turning Basins, Locations Approximate
- Gowanus Canal

Notes:

- Survey conducted by CR Environmental, Inc., January 2010
- Hatched areas were not evaluated because ice in the turning basins and the presence of several barges prevented completion of the 2010 survey
- Vertical Scale - NAVD88, US Survey Feet (Estimated)

FIGURE 3-1a
Bathymetric Map of Gowanus Canal
Upper Canal
Gowanus Canal Remedial Investigation
Brooklyn, New York

FIGURE 3-1b
Bathymetric Map of Gowanus Canal
Middle Canal
Gowanus Canal Remedial Investigation
Brooklyn, New York

FIGURE 3-1c
Bathymetric Map of Gowanus Canal
Lower Canal
Gowanus Canal Remedial Investigation
Brooklyn, New York

FIGURE 3-2a
Plan View of Bathymetric Differences 2003 - 2010
Upper Canal
Gowanus Canal Remedial Investigation
Brooklyn, New York

FIGURE 3-2b
Plan View of Bathymetric Differences 2003 - 2010
Middle Canal
Gowanus Canal Remedial Investigation
Brooklyn, New York

FIGURE 3-2c
 Plan View of Bathymetric Differences 2003 - 2010
 Lower Canal
 Gowanus Canal Remedial Investigation
 Brooklyn, New York

Notes:
 Approximately 100x vertical exaggeration used to illustrate small differences in elevation.
 Survey data collected by CR Environmental, Inc (East Falmouth, Massachusetts) on June 25, 2003 and January 5, 2010

FIGURE 3-3
 Cross Section of Bathymetric Differences 2003-2010
 Gowanus Canal Remedial Investigation
 Brooklyn, New York

Barge was removed in early 2010 to accommodate the installation of the aeration pipe by NYC DEP

Legend

- Side Scan Sonar Target
- Magnetometer Target
- ▬ Flushing Tunnel
- ▬ Barges, Floating Docks, Boats
- - - Debris Areas
- ▭ Gravel
- ▨ Infilled Turning Basins, Locations Approximate
- ▭ Gowanus Canal

Notes:

1. Survey for debris, barges, floating docks and boats conducted by OSI, 2005
2. The bottom of the canal was generally covered with gravel from the barge located between 4th and 5th Streets to just south of the Hamilton Street Bridge. Gravel was generally not observed within the turning basins
3. Gravel delineation is based on 2010 field observations

See Note 2

FIGURE 3-4a
 Map of Debris and Obstructions in Gowanus Canal in 2005
 Upper Canal
 Gowanus Canal
 Brooklyn, New York

Notes:

1. Survey for debris, barges, floating docks and boats conducted by OSI, 2005
2. The bottom of the canal was generally covered with gravel from the barge located between 4th and 5th Streets to just south of the Hamilton Street Bridge. Gravel was generally not observed within the turning basins
3. Gravel delineation is based on 2010 field observations

FIGURE 3-4b
 Map of Debris and Obstructions in Gowanus Canal in 2005
 Middle Canal
 Gowanus Canal
 Brooklyn, New York

FIGURE 3-4c
 Map of Debris and Obstructions in Gowanus Canal in 2005
 Lower Canal
 Gowanus Canal
 Brooklyn, New York

FIGURE 3-4d
 Map of Debris and Obstructions in Gowanus Canal in 2010
 Upper Canal
 Gowanus Canal
 Brooklyn, New York

Side Scan Sonar Target No.	Description
9a	Scattered debris
11	Pile of large blocks and debris
11a	Pile of debris
11b	Long pile of rip rap
35	Scattered debris
37	Long section of rubble and rip rap
37a	Sunken barge
37b	Barge hull and small boat wreck
37c	Two hard rectangular features
39	Two rectangular objects
42	Pile of rip rap
42a	Box-like object
42b	Pile of rip rap
48	Scattered debris

The complete side scan sonar survey report with imagery is provided in Appendix M.

FIGURE 3-4e
 Map of Debris and Obstructions in Gowanus Canal in 2010
 Middle Canal
 Gowanus Canal
 Brooklyn, New York

Side Scan Sonar Target No.	Description
2	Hard square object
2a	Rectangular object - possible automobile
2b	Rectangular object - possible automobile
3	Hard linear feature
5	Linear scattered debris
9	Rectangular feature
9a	Scattered debris
48	Scattered debris
52	Numerous circular features, suspected tires

The complete side scan sonar survey report with imagery is provided in Appendix M.

Legend

- 2010 Side Scan Sonar Target
- Gowanus Canal

Notes:
 1. Survey for debris and cultural resources conducted by Dolan Engineering, 2010

FIGURE 3-4f
 Map of Debris and Obstructions in Gowanus Canal in 2010
 Lower Canal
 Gowanus Canal
 Brooklyn, New York

FIGURE 3-5a
Map of Thickness of Soft Sediment Layer
Upper Canal
Gowanus Canal Remedial Investigation
Brooklyn, New York

Legend

- USEPA 2010 Coring Locations
- Soft Sediment Thickness (ft)
- █ Gowanus Canal

Note:
Soft sediment thickness is corrected for less than 100 percent core recovery

FIGURE 3-5b
Map of Thickness of Soft Sediment Layer
Middle Canal
Gowanus Canal Remedial Investigation
Brooklyn, New York

FIGURE 3-5c
Map of Thickness of Soft Sediment Layer
Lower Canal
Gowanus Canal Remedial Investigation
Brooklyn, New York

FIGURE 3-6a
Map of Elevation of Top of Native Sediment Unit
Upper Canal
Gowanus Canal Remedial Investigation
Brooklyn, New York

FIGURE 3-6b
Map of Elevation of Top of Native Sediment Unit
Middle Canal
Gowanus Canal Remedial Investigation
Brooklyn, New York

FIGURE 3-6c
Map of Elevation of Top of Native Sediment Unit
Lower Canal
Gowanus Canal Remedial Investigation
Brooklyn, New York

Head of canal at low tide (top), note exposed sediment at right of photo and aeration pipe under construction by NYC. Example of crib-type bulkhead and floating boat docks observed in canal (bottom); this location is on the west side of the canal, immediately south of Carroll Street.

FIGURE 3-7a
Representative Photos of the Gowanus Canal Shoreline
Gowanus Canal Remedial Investigation
Brooklyn, New York

Example of sheet pile bulkheading along with a section of aeration pipe on the east side of the canal between Union and Carroll Streets (top). Example of newer wooden crib-type bulkhead (bottom).

FIGURE 3-7b
Representative Photos of the Gowanus Canal Shoreline
Gowanus Canal Remedial Investigation
Brooklyn, New York

Degraded bulkheads in middle reach of canal, near the end of Bond Street.

FIGURE 3-7c
Representative Photos of the Gowanus Canal Shoreline
Gowanus Canal Remedial Investigation
Brooklyn, New York

View to the south (top) and north (bottom) of the western shoreline south of the Hamilton Avenue Bridge. Note bulkhead structures in distance in both photos

FIGURE 3-7d
Representative Photos of the Gowanus Canal Shoreline
Gowanus Canal Remedial Investigation
Brooklyn, New York

End of DeGraw Street on western side of canal; note downed tree and other debris in water at left of photograph (left). Right photograph shows the mouth of the 4th Street Turning Basin,

FIGURE 3-7e
Representative Photos of the Gowanus Canal Shoreline
Gowanus Canal Remedial Investigation
Brooklyn, New York

Figure 3-8a
CSO and Other Pipe Outfall Locations
Gowanus Canal Remedial Investigation
Brooklyn, New York

Figure 3-8b
 CSO and Other Pipe Outfall Locations
 Gowanus Canal Remedial Investigation
 Brooklyn, New York

Figure 3-8c
 CSO and Other Pipe Outfall Locations
 Gowanus Canal Remedial Investigation
 Brooklyn, New York

Figure 3-8d
 CSO and Other Pipe Outfall Locations
 Gowanus Canal Remedial Investigation
 Brooklyn, New York

Figure 3-8e
 CSO and Other Pipe Outfall Locations
 Gowanus Canal Remedial Investigation
 Brooklyn, New York

Figure 3-8f
 CSO and Other Pipe Outfall Locations
 Gowanus Canal Remedial Investigation
 Brooklyn, New York

Figure 3-8g
 CSO and Other Pipe Outfall Locations
 Gowanus Canal Remedial Investigation
 Brooklyn, New York

Figure 3-8h
CSO and Other Pipe Outfall Locations
Gowanus Canal Remedial Investigation
Brooklyn, New York

FIGURE 3-9
 Study Area Geologic Cross-Section Location Map
 (A-A' through E-E')
 Gowanus Canal Remedial Investigation
 Brooklyn, New York

FIGURE 3-10b
 Geologic Cross-Section (B-B')
 Gowanus Canal Remedial Investigation
 Brooklyn, New York

FIGURE 3-10c
 Geologic Cross-Section (C-C')
 Gowanus Canal Remedial Investigation
 Brooklyn, New York

FIGURE 3-10d
 Geologic Cross-Section (D-D')
 Gowanus Canal Remedial Investigation
 Brooklyn, New York

FIGURE 3-11a
 Shallow Groundwater Elevations
 July 26, 2010 @ 9-10 am
 High Tide
 Gowanus Canal Remedial Investigation
 Brooklyn, New York

FIGURE 3-11b
 Shallow Groundwater Elevations
 August 23, 2010
 Low Tide
 Gowanus Canal Remedial Investigation
 Brooklyn, New York

FIGURE 3-11d
 Shallow Groundwater Elevations
 October 22, 2010 @ 2-3pm
 Low Tide
 Gowanus Canal Remedial Investigation
 Brooklyn, New York

FIGURE 3-11e
 Shallow Groundwater Elevations
 November 22, 2010 @ 10am-12pm
 Low Tide
 Gowanus Canal Remedial Investigation
 Brooklyn, New York

FIGURE 3-11f
 Shallow Groundwater Elevations
 December 20, 2010 @ 1-3pm
 Low Tide
 Gowanus Canal Remedial Investigation
 Brooklyn, New York

FIGURE 3-11g
 Intermediate Groundwater Elevations
 July 26, 2010 @ 9-10am
 High Tide
 Gowanus Canal Remedial Investigation
 Brooklyn, New York

FIGURE 3-11h
 Intermediate Groundwater Elevations
 August 23, 2010
 Low Tide
 Gowanus Canal Remedial Investigation
 Brooklyn, New York

Legend

- 2.70 Groundwater Elevation (ft NAVD88)
- ➔ Inferred Groundwater Flow Direction
- Existing Monitoring Well Installed by National Grid
- Monitor Well Pair Installed by New York City
- Monitor Well Pair Installed by National Grid
- Monitor Well Pair Installed by USEPA
- Flushing Tunnel
- ▨ Infilled Turning Basins, Locations Approximate
- Gowanus Canal

FIGURE 3-11i
 Intermediate Groundwater Elevations
 September 29, 2010 @ 12-1pm
 High Tide
 Gowanus Canal Remedial Investigation
 Brooklyn, New York

FIGURE 3-11j
 Intermediate Groundwater Elevations
 October 22, 2010 @ 2-3pm
 Low Tide
 Gowanus Canal Remedial Investigation
 Brooklyn, New York

FIGURE 3-11k
 Intermediate Groundwater Elevations
 November 22, 2010 @ 10am-12pm
 Low Tide
 Gowanus Canal Remedial Investigation
 Brooklyn, New York

FIGURE 3-111
 Intermediate Groundwater Elevations
 December 20, 2010 @ 1:3pm
 Low Tide
 Gowanus Canal Remedial Investigation
 Brooklyn, New York

